

Asphalt Innovation Symposium 2025

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Antwerp

University of Antwerp
| SuPAR | Sustainable Pavements
and Asphalt Research

University
of Antwerp

Sessie 2C Emission Current Practices in Emission Measurement in the Dutch Asphalt Sector: Insights from the InnovA58 Test Section

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Dutch asphalt sector: Transition towards 2050

- **Increasing reclaimed asphalt (RA) content in new mix**
 - RA on surface layers
 - 25-30% PR in SMA and DZOAB without rejuvenator
 - 40-60% PR in SMA and DZOAB with rejuvenator
- **Producing asphalt at low temperature**
 - <140 °C warm mix asphalt
 - <110 °C half warm asphalt-with foaming technology
- **Changes and quality aspects of asphalt binder**
 - Biobased binder
 - Alternative binders

Dé weg naar
fossielvrij asfalt.

Innovations and environmental impact

Potential for carbon footprint reduction

Responsible innovation:

Combining LCA (environmental impact) with SHE (safety, health and environment)

Emissions during different phases of asphalt pavement

Fumes in asphalt production

Fumes are fine solid or liquid particles (aerosols) suspended in air, accompanied by gases/vapours and volatile organic compound (VOCs).

- Heating bitumen, asphalt emits fumes
- Fumes arise from volatilization and thermal breakdown
- Exposure to fumes may cause health risks

Fume exposure measurement by Dutch industry

Protocol: Dutch asphalt contractors (VBW) uses a collective protocol to measure exposure to fumes.

Purpose: supports health and safety improvements in the sector through data collection, and comparability.

Sampling methods

- PAS: measures individual worker exposure using air pumps attached to clothing.
- STAT: captures ambient concentrations at a fixed point above the screed.
- Sampling duration: 4 hours

Assesses asphalt fumes, aldehydes, PAH → conventional asphalt

Emission assessment workflow

Assessment approach for new innovation → material/ process

InnovA58

▪ Scope

- Test section for demonstration of Innovative sustainable solutions.
- Four surface layers with RA (60% wt.) and four rejuvenators in porous asphalt (DZOAB)

▪ Emissions research

- Identify emissions from individual binder components and asphalt mixtures.
- Evaluate VOC and SVOCs.

Phase 1: Emissions from binder components

- **Samples:** commercial rejuvenators (4), softener (1), fresh bitumen (3), binder from RA.
- **Analytical method**
 - GC-MS for chemical profiling;
 - FTIR for real-time gas monitoring.

50°C to 200°C

0.5 L/min

Compound Identification (GC-MS with NIST Library)

140

File :D:\Data\Gerstel_2022\Asfalt\22ACM140_Blank.D
 Operator : PD
 Acquired : 30 Sep 22 03:53 pm using AcqMethod EI_scan.M
 Instrument : GC-MS
 Sample Name : 22ACM140_Blank
 Misc Info :
 Vial Number: 4

GC chromatogram

Mass spectrum

Nonanal NIST match 944/999

CCCCCCCC=O

- analyzed @140°C, 180°C, 200°C.
- alkanes, aldehydes, hydrocarbons

Phase 2: Asphalt mixing & cooling

- **Sample:** mixtures with rejuvenators (4), with softner (1) and another with softer bitumen (PEN 160/220).
- **Approach**
 - Aggregates/bitumen pre-heated to 145–155°C, rejuvenators added and mixed.
 - Emissions captured with “Tenax tubes” during mixing and cooling.
 - Analysis: GC-MS (tracks Phase 1 compounds); FTIR (monitors trends during cooling).

Traces at the mixture level

GC-MS

FTIR

Insights and on-going projects

- Map emissions with FTIR and GC-MS for both binder and mixture level
- Demonstrate differences in emission profiles characteristics to components and between phases
- Common emissions: Alkanes, alkenes, aldehyde, aromatics and temperature has clearly an influence